

Biosorption of copper(II) and manganese(II) from waste water using low cost bio adsorbents

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Abstract: Two low cost bio adsorbents such as corn cob (CC) and Strychnospotatorum seed powder (SPSP) were used for the removal of copper(II) and manganese(II) from industrial waste water and presented in this paper. Raw powders of the two adsorbents were prepared and used for the study. Batch adsorption experimentation was adopted to investigate the adsorption kinetics, isothermal studies and removal efficiency of the two adsorbents. Effect of pH, contact time, initial metal concentration and temperature were also studied. Adsorption of copper(II) and manganese(II) was optimized at a pH of 5, temperature of 40°C, in a time period of 60 min using the two adsorbents. By using CC and SPSP as adsorbents 99.7% of copper(II) and 99.8% of manganese(II) were removed. This was achieved by using 0.4 g dosage of the adsorbents. Removal of copper(II) and manganese(II) followed pseudo-second order reaction kinetics. Isothermal studies indicated that the removal the selected heavy metals follows Langmuir adsorption isotherm model. Maximum adsorption capacity was found to be 6.24 mg/g for the two adsorbents. These adsorbents were found to be advantageous in removing the chosen metals from water as they avoid laborious and time consuming chemical treatment methods. Hence the method was found to be cost effective, efficient, advantageous and simple.

Keywords: Copper(II), manganese(II), Langmuir isotherms, pseudo-first order reactions, pseudo-second order reaction, corn cob, strychnospotatorum seed powder.

Introduction

Human activities such as mining, metal processing, pharmaceuticals, organic chemicals, rubber, plastics, waste accumulation, industrial activities and the use of agrochemicals (fertilizers and pesticides) have caused extensive contamination of both surface and groundwater with toxic heavy metals¹. It is because the toxic substances have a tendency to accumulate in soil, sea water, fresh water and sediments due to their high dispersion from where they enter into food chain². It is known that eleven metals namely lead, chromium, mercury, uranium, cesium, zinc, cadmium, copper, nickel, cobalt and arsenic out of twenty classified metals are referred to as toxic and are released into the environment in quantities which pose serious risks to human health³. Copper is a hazardous heavy metal that is used in various industries

such as smelting, plating, electroplating, manufacture of brass and copper based agro chemicals. Though copper at a low concentration is essential for living organisms, at higher concentration it becomes potentially toxic. Copper toxicity, also called copperiosis, refers to the consequences of excess of copper in the body⁴. Copper toxicity can occur as a result of intake of food and water containing excess of copper. Further copper does not degrade in the environment and its presence in the soil adversely impacts the activities of microorganisms thereby slowing down the decomposition of organic matter⁵. Besides copper manganese also has an adverse effect on human health and environment when released into environment. The removal of heavy metal from waste water has received a great deal of attention in recent years⁶. Several conventional, physical and chemical

waste water treatment technologies including coagulation, filtration, evaporation recovery, precipitation, oxidation, reduction, electrochemical treatment ion exchange, and reverse osmosis have been used to remove heavy metals from aqueous systems. However, these methods are costly, technically complicated and are only used in special cases of waste water treatments⁷. Moreover most of these processes are only effective when there are high levels of metals in aqueous solutions. There has recently been increased interest in the development of new materials capable of removing toxic heavy metals from contaminated water⁸. The sorption process which includes metal immobilization in contaminated water has gained attention in the past few decades because it offers advantages such as high efficiency and low operating cost and these methods are ecofriendly when compared to conventional methods⁹. In literature it was found that various bio adsorbents such as potato¹⁰, banana peel¹⁰, fly ash¹¹, bajra agro waste⁵, egg shell¹², chicken egg shell¹³, saw dust¹⁴, coconut coir¹⁵, oil palm empty fruit bunch¹⁵, sugar cane bagasse¹⁶, pumpkins¹⁷, water melon shell¹⁸, peanut husk¹⁹, groundnut shell²⁰, activated carbon²¹ were used as low cost adsorbents for the removal of various heavy metals. In all the cited works, the adsorbents chosen were converted thermally to carbon and then subjected to batch experimental techniques. A preliminary experimentation was carried out by the authors to evaluate the removal efficiency of two low cost adsorbents like corn cob (CC) and *Strychnos potatorum* seed powder (SPSP) in raw form. For the present study the authors had chosen two potentially toxic metals such as copper(II) and manganese(II). The adsorbents chosen by the authors found to be effective in removing selected metals by a cost effective and ecofriendly technique.

Experimental

Materials and methods:

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade Merck make. Double distilled water was used throughout the experiment. High-performance atomic absorption

(AA) spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer make), the PinAAcle900H is a combined flame/deuterium furnace system with continuum source background correction. VERTEX 70/70v FTIR spectrophotometer of Bruker make was used for FTIR analysis of the samples.

Preparation of metal salt solutions: Adequate amounts of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were accurately weighed and prepared a solution of concentration 100 mg L^{-1} . Series of varying concentrated solutions were prepared by proper dilutions.

Preparation of adsorbents:

Adsorbents for the present study such as CC and SPSP were collected from the local markets. These were washed with water and dried at room temperature. The dried material was crushed and ground to a fine powder. Such powder was sieved through 5 μ mesh. The resulting powdered sample was used for adsorption studies.

Characterization of adsorbents:

The adsorbents are characterized by the functional groups present in the surface. In most of the bio adsorbents phenolic groups, hydroxyl groups, carbonyl groups and lactone groups are present. FTIR spectrum of the two adsorbents suggests that these adsorbents contain the groups mentioned above. The presence of these functional groups infers the efficiency of the adsorbents in removing heavy metals which bind to those functional groups. FTIR spectra of the two adsorbents were presented (Supplementary Figs. S1 and S2). The surface area of the two adsorbents was found to be 455 and 475 $\text{m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$. These values were found to be higher than that of carbon supports the increased efficiency of the adsorbents.

Batch adsorption procedures:

Preliminary experimentation was carried out to establish the conditions for efficient and effective removal of heavy metals from waste water. Initially 1 g of the adsorbent was mixed with 50 ml of the metal salt solution and the mixture was agitated for 120 min. Concentration of the metal remained after

the pre-determined time was calculated using AAS. Afterwards effect of pH, contact time, initial metal concentration and adsorbent dosage were investigated. It was found that copper can be removed from waste water effectively (99.7%) at pH 5, 40°C, 60 min by using 0.4 g of CC and SPSP. The percent removal of manganese by CC and SPSP seed powder was found to be 99.8 at the same operating conditions of used for the removal of copper(II). pH of the solution was adjusted by using 0.1 N HCl and 0.1 N NaOH solutions.

Results and discussion

Effect of pH:

One of the most important parameters which regulate the adsorption of heavy metals using bio adsorbents is pH of the solution. It determines the surface charge of the adsorbent and degree of ionization and speciation of the adsorbate. The percent removal of the metals at different pH values were plotted and represented in Fig. 1. The results indicated that the removal of copper and manganese were optimized at a pH of 5 with CC and SPSP. The highest percentage removal of the metals was observed at the pH values. An increase in pH showed a

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on the removal of the selected heavy metals using the two adsorbents.

significant increase in the adsorption of copper was observed. Over pH value of 8 precipitation of copper was noticed. Hence the removal of copper and manganese by the adsorbents was optimized at pH 5.

Effect of temperature:

The effect of temperature on the removal efficiency of the two metal ions from the aqueous solution using different adsorbents was studied. The results were shown in Fig. 2. A series of experiments were carried out to establish the equilibrium temperature for the effective removal of copper and manganese ions using the adsorbents. By fixing the adsorbent dosage, contact time, pH and initial metal concentration batch experiments were carried out at varying temperatures. From the results obtained it was found at a temperature of 40°C is optimum for the highest percent removal of the metals.

Fig. 2. Effect of temperature on the removal of selected heavy metals using the two adsorbents.

Effect of contact time:

Effect of contact time on the removal of copper and manganese using the two adsorbents was studied. The results were represented in Fig. 3. From the results it was found that the highest percent removal of the metals was observed in 60 min. Hence 60 min was fixed as optimum contact time for the present study.

Fig. 3. Effect of contact time for the removal of selected heavy metals using two adsorbents.

Effect of adsorbent dosage:

A series of experiments were carried out to ascertain the adsorbent dosage for the efficient removal copper and manganese by the two adsorbents. The experiments were conducted by taking 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1.0 g of the adsorbents for batch studies. The results obtained were shown in Fig. 4. From the results it was found that removal of copper and manganese from aqueous solution was effective for 0.4 g of the adsorbents, and the same was fixed as optimum adsorbent dosage.

Fig. 4. Effect of adsorbent dosage on the removal of selected heavy metals using two adsorbents.

Effect of initial metal ion concentration:

A study was carried out to fix the initial metal ion concentration by varying the metal concentration and by fixing adsorbent dosage, pH and contact time. A series of copper and manganese ion solutions of concentration 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90 mg L⁻¹ were mixed in separate flasks with 0.4 g of the adsorbents. Concentration of copper and manganese in the filtrate was determined after 60 min. From the results it was clear that the removal of the metals from aqueous solution decreases as the metal ion concentration increases. The maximum removal of copper and manganese using the adsorbents was found at a metal concentration of 10 mg L⁻¹.

Adsorption isotherms:

These are important in describing the behavior of adsorbate-adsorbent interaction. This is in turn useful for the purposes of designing an adsorption process. There are many adsorption isotherms are used for this purpose. In the present study Langmuir adsorption isotherm and Freundlich adsorption isotherms were adopted.

Langmuir adsorption isotherm:

The Langmuir adsorption isotherm is defined as

$$q_e = \frac{q_m K C_e}{1 + K C_e}$$

And in linearized form the same is

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{q_{max} K_L} + \frac{C_e}{q_{max}}$$

where q_m and K are Langmuir constants related to the sorption capacity and sorption energy respectively. C_e is the equilibrium concentration in mg L⁻¹ and Q_e is the amount of adsorbate adsorbed per unit weight of adsorbent. The adsorption of copper on different adsorbents gives a straight line. It is clear that a linear fit is fairly good. This enables the Langmuir adsorption isotherm model's applicability.

Freundlich adsorption isotherm:

The Freundlich isotherm is defined as

Table 1. Isothermal characteristics, kinetic study characteristics, batch adsorption parameters for the removal of copper(II) and manganese(II) using CC and SPSP

Sl. No.	Description	Parameter		Value observed		Value observed
1.	Langmuir adsorption isotherm characteristics	Q_m (mg/g)	Removal of copper using	1.014	Removal of manganese using	0.9755
		b	CC and SPSP	5943.7	CC and SPSP	14302.55
		R^2		0.9989		0.9997
2.	Fruendlich adsorption isotherm characteristics	n	Removal of copper using	2.12	Removal of manganese using CC	2.23
		K_L	CC	26.5		26.3
		R^2		0.45		0.403
		n	Removal of copper using	2.12	Removal of manganese using SPSP	2.21
		K_L	SPSP	25.8		26.2
3.	Pseudo-second order kinetics	Q_e (mg/g)	Removal of copper using	0.602	Removal of manganese using	0.602
		k_2	CC and SPSP	10.35	CC and SPSP	10.35
4.	Batch adsorption characteristics	pH	Removal of	5	Removal of	5
		Temperature (°C)	manganese	40	manganese	40
		Contact time (min)	using CC	60	using CC	60
		Adsorbent dose (g)	and SPSP	0.4	and SPSP	0.4

$$q_e = K_F C_e^{1/n}$$

And in linearized form

$$\log q_e = \log K_F + \frac{1}{n} \log C_e$$

where C_e is the equilibrium concentration in mg L^{-1} , q_e is the amount of adsorbate adsorbed per unit weight of adsorbent in mg g^{-1} and “ k ” is parameter related to the temperature and “ n ” is a characteristic constant for the adsorption. The plots for $\log q_e$ against $\log C_e$ are presented as supplementary data. The Freundlich isotherm constants and correlation data was presented in Table 1.

From the results it was found that the removal of copper and manganese using CC and SPSP seed powder followed Langmuir adsorption isotherm model with an R squared value of 0.988.

Adsorption kinetics:

The mechanism by which the metal ions adsorb on the different adsorbents is clearly understood by kinetic studies. For the present study pseudo-first

order and pseudo-second order kinetic models were used to study the kinetics of adsorption of copper and manganese on the two adsorbents. From the results it was found that adsorption of copper and manganese by CC and SPSP obeyed pseudo-second order kinetics. A plot between t/q_t and t showed in Fig. 5 and found to be linear with an R squared value of 1. Hence it is implicated that the adsorption process followed pseudo-second order kinetics. A

Fig. 5. Pseudo-second order kinetic model for the removal of copper and manganese using CC and SPSP seed powder.

Table 2. Comparative table for the removal of Cu^{II} using various adsorbents

Sl. No.	Name of the adsorbent	Q _e (mg/g)	Remarks
1.	Durian tree sawdust	18.42	All these materials are either chemically treated or carbonized before proceeding for adsorption or removal of heavy metals
2.	Coconut coir	18.38	
3.	Oil palm empty fruit bunch	26.95	
4.	Scoria	27.81	
5.	Populous deltoids leaves	17.76	
6.	Syzygiumcumini leaves	15.87	
7.	Eichhorniacrassipes	32.51	
8.	Chitosan-tripolyphosphate	26.06	
9.	Jujube complex bead	3.06	
10.	Modified carrot residues	32.74	
11.	Modified fir tree sawdust	12.7	
12.	Modified poplar tree sawdust	6.92	
13.	p(AMPS) hydrogel	100.8	
14.	Magnetic p(AMPS) composite hydrogels	105.6	
15.	Natural bentonite	7.9	
16.	Natural zeolite	8.9	
17.	Kaolinite	10.7	
18.	Cellulose	7.0	
19.	Peanut hull carbon	65.5	
20.	Activated carbon	4.4	
21.	Pretreated fish bones	150.7	
22.	Soya beanhulls	38.7	
23.	Carrotresidue	32.74	
24.	Ilgin lignite	32.28	
25.	Sugar beet pulp	30.9	
26.	Sourorange residue	21.7	
27.	Apple wastes	10.8	
28.	Walnut shell	6.74	
29.	Hazel nut shell	6.65	
30.	Activated carbon AQ-30	6.3	
31.	Almond shell	3.62	
32.	Banana peel	4.75	
33.	Sawdust	1.79	
34.	Egg shell	172.41	
35.	UA	113.63	
36.	EG+UA	128.20	
37.	Sawdust @ 30 C	37.17	
38.	Sawdust @ 40 C	34.84	
39.	Sawdust @ 50 C	34.13	
40.	Sawdust @ 60 C	30.67	
41.	Coconut tree sawdust	3.89	
42.	Egg shell	34.58	

Table-2 (contd.)

43.	Sugarcane bagasse	3.65	
44.	Watermelon shell	111.1	
45.	Present study	6.24	Uncarbonized

Table 3. Comparative study for the removal of Mn^{II} using various adsorbents

Sl. No.	Name of the adsorbent used	Q _e (mg/g)	Remarks
1.	Activated carbon	3.49	All these materials are either chemically treated or carbonized before proceeding for adsorption or removal of heavy metals
2.	Activated carbon from agro residues	6.66	
3.	Birbira leaves	3.41	
4.	Modified clays	6.33	
5.	Rice husk	301	
6.	Graphene oxide	41.67	
7.	Bone charcoal	29.56	
8.	Maize stalks	16.61	
9.	Present study	6.24	

comparative study between the present adsorbents and other adsorbents used in literature is presented in Tables 2 and 3.

Highlights of the present study:

In literature all the adsorption methods which involve the removal of heavy metals using bio sorbents was carried out either by converting the bio material into activated carbon (carbonization) or by chemical pretreatment methods. The present method avoids any of the two mentioned. The maximum adsorption capacity in the removal of Cu^{II} and Mn^{II} were found to be 6.24 mg/g using the two bio adsorbents in their raw form (without any chemical pretreatment). This was found to be good in accordance with the literature cited as all those materials are carbonized. The present method was found to be simple, easy and convenient with high efficiency.

Conclusions

The presence of heavy metals beyond the prescribed standard limits is vulnerable to human health. Hence it is important to eliminate contamination of water with such substances. Bio adsorbents gained prominence during recent years. In light of this an

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attempt was made to remove copper(II) and manganese(II) from waste water using CC and SPSP in the raw form. Copper(II) and manganese(II) were found to be effectively and efficiently removed by using the selected adsorbents. Copper(II) and manganese(II) were removed efficiently by CC and SPSP with a percent removal of 99.7% and 99.8% respectively. Langmuir adsorption isotherm fitted the best for the present study. The mechanism of adsorption followed pseudo-second order kinetics. The advantage of the present method is that the adsorbents were used without any chemical or pretreatment methods.

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